

Investigating Affordances in Networks of “Things”, “Performers”, and “Composers”: The Multimodal Lab as Site of Knowledge Production

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Abstract

This paper builds on a lecture delivered at the Transplanted Roots Percussion Research Symposium (Porto, 2025) and presents findings from a two-day artistic research lab—the first experiment of my doctoral project. The lab explored collaborative entanglements among “performer”, “composer”, and musicking technology, grounded in theories by Rheinberger, de Assis, Gibson, and Barad. Centred on a DIY cassette-tape apparatus, it employed a multimodal approach combining performance, reflection, documentation, and conversation, supported by video, photography, field notes, and ethnographic protocols. The study investigates how roles, affordances, and material agencies emerge through intra-action, demonstrating how knowledge arises not from outcomes but through the unfolding processes of experimentation.

Introduction to My Experimental System

In February of 2025, I conducted a two-day artistic research laboratory (*OpenLab#1.1*) as part of my ongoing doctoral project—the first in a series of experiments belonging to my derived experimental system, where I ask a new “composer” to choose a working concept to explore together—an aesthetic research—while I look microscopically at the interaction and social dynamic—an epistemic research. As a part of my experimental system, I ask that each composer incorporate cassette tape, in any way and with any tools they choose. (While I use the term composer and performer for analytical purposes in my research, they are merely points of departure. Composer and performer are fundamentally understood as fluid, unstable assignments.)

The collaborators in *OpenLab#1.1* included myself (as percussionist and researcher), composer and live-electronics musician Dustin Zorn, and a nonhuman participant: a DIY cassette-tape-reading apparatus built specifically for the lab. Documentary materials included video, multi-channel audio, photographs, annotated lab books, and an ethnographic observation protocol. Central to the lab’s documentation method were what I refer to as reflection-in-action pauses—timed interruptions (every 5–20 minutes) during which an audio cue prompted each collaborator to momentarily stop, reflect, and record spontaneous impressions. These micro-temporal snapshots formed an additional

experiential layer within the data set, offering insight into the shifting feelings, hesitations, and micro-decisions unfolding throughout the process (for further information on reflection-in/on-action, see Schön (1983).)

Figure 1 illustrates the prototype that Dustin initially conceptualized: a plastic ruler mounted on a wooden base with sliding dowels, tape heads, and looping cassette tape—part ruler, part instrument, part sculpture. This model would be iterated four times to create a four-channel instrument or apparatus. Figure 2 shows our final setup with the apparatus in use.

Figure 1: Graphic illustration of the cassette-looping apparatus prototype, courtesy of Dustin Zorn.

Figure 2: The final setup at the end of *OpenLab#1.1* with Dustin Zorn (left) and Katelyn Rose King (right).

Theoretical Framework: Rheinberger, de Assis and a Multimodal Approach

My doctoral project is methodologically grounded in Hans-Jörg Rheinberger’s concept of the *experimental system* (Rheinberger 2006). Rheinberger conceives laboratories as generative constellations of instruments, materials, and ideas that yield unforeseen epistemic events. Within such systems, epistemic things—unstable, not-yet-understood phenomena—coexist with technical objects, the stabilized tools that enable further experimentation. Over the course of repeated experiments, these roles may shift: what initially appears as an epistemic thing can become a technical object, and vice versa. Crucially,

an experiment's success lies not in providing definitive answers but in generating new questions that feed back into the evolving research system.

Paulo de Assis (2018) extends this framework into musical artistic research, offering a compelling way to transpose natural-science methodologies into music compositional practice. He invites us to regard composition, rehearsal, and performance as experimental sites where artistic processes unfold through re-performance, reinterpretation, and re-materialization. Rather than treating musical works as fixed entities, de Assis frames them as assemblages of strata—conceptual, material, performative, and documentary. The experiment in de Assis' work acts as a new mode of creation.

Building on these ideas, my labs function as dynamic experimental systems that shift between different modes of doing: building, experimentation, composition, performance, and presentation. These transitions are not merely procedural but epistemic, generating new forms of knowledge through iterative practice.

Wolfgang Heiniger argues that contemporary music is best understood as a multi-modal practice—one that engages not only with sound material but also with relationships, particularly the relational networks produced by digital devices and interfaces in everyday life (2019). The term multimodality, originating in social semiotics (Kress and Leeuwen 2001), refers to communication that interweaves multiple meaning systems, including language, sound, image, bodily gesture, spatial arrangements, and material cultures. Digital technologies intensify these interconnections by making diverse modes accessible within a single medium.

In my labs, I use the term multimodal in three senses:

- As a multi-sensory approach, where visual, sonic, and haptic elements interact.
- As a mode of creation, encompassing the generation of artistic ideas as well as the articulation of knowledge and research questions.
- As shifting modes of doing, moving between building, experimentation, composition, performance, and presentation.

The following observations stem from *OpenLab#1.1* and will contribute to the overall analysis of my experimental system during the concluding stages of my doctoral project.

Observations from *OpenLab#1.1*

Roles, Patterns of Characteristics, and Temporality

The first key observation concerns the instability of roles. Throughout the lab, I shifted among performer, organizer, co-builder, and researcher. These role transitions produced intra-role conflicts, particularly when logistical tasks disrupted musical flow or when documentation demands interfered with co-creation. Dustin similarly expressed tension around responsibilities, seeking clarity that ultimately proved incompatible with the unfolding nature of the process.

Certain patterns of characteristics, or perhaps markers of contingent relations, appeared in various forms. For example, self-presentation was marked differently by each of us: Dustin always recorded his face while making his reflections, I always recorded the objects. Dustin more-often vocally exclaimed his “failures”, while I tended to vocalise my “successes”.

Time, too, emerged as a structuring force. Our collective sense of urgency fluctuated visibly, tracked on a shared whiteboard as tasks accumulated. Calm beginnings gave way to compressed timelines, driven by building closing hours and the approaching open session. This tacit temporal dramaturgy shaped the affective and productive atmosphere of the lab, but was collectively formed and shaped.

Affordances

Initially, I expected the core focus to be the affordances of the newly built cassette apparatus. Drawing from James J. Gibson’s ecological psychology (1979), affordances describe relational action possibilities between an organism and its environment. Yet because the apparatus was in a continuous state of becoming, its affordances shifted unpredictably.

Instead, the more salient phenomenon was the mutual affordances we granted one another. Dustin assumed I possessed extensive tape-loop expertise, which expanded my own sense of capability. Conversely, my expectation that percussion elements would arise led to intra-role conflicts when they did not. These relational affordances became epistemic things, producing new artistic behaviours and insights.

Material Agency

Material agency played a decisive role throughout the lab. Drawing on Jane Bennett’s concept of vibrant matter (2009) and Andrew Pickering’s mangle-of-practice (1995), the apparatus demonstrated liveliness: loops slipped, electronics malfunctioned, tape tension fluctuated, and drill bits resisted. These disruptions demanded improvisation, reconfiguration, and embodied negotiation.

A particularly illustrative example involved attaching a tape head to the wooden base. The process required a coordinated, choreographic entanglement of human bodies, tools, and materials. In another example, Figure 3 shows how the apparatus pulled our audience in towards a try-out session and discussion on tactile improvements. In these moments, technical objects became epistemic as their resistances and limits generated new questions and pathways.

Intra-action in Collective Composition

As a performer-collaborator, I am trying to rewrite my codes around collective composition by meditating on Karen Barad’s notion of intra-action (2007). Unlike interaction, where pre-existing entities meet and react to one another, intra-action means entities emerge through relation. For Barad, agency is not something possessed; it arises in entangled doing. But for Barad, this means that entities are in fact those relations and

Figure 3: Group discussion and try-outs during the open-doors final hour of *OpenLab#1.1*.

encounters they find themselves in. One is not an independent entity, but the existence of the presence of others.

In our lab, “percussionist”, “composer”, and “apparatus” were not predefined roles but effects of ongoing entanglement. The apparatus itself enacted cuts—moments that defined what could or couldn’t occur. When a tape loop snapped mid-performance, we didn’t repair it: the break became part of the piece. Such moments weren’t failures but transformations that redefined the system’s possibilities.

Through this lens, epistemic things and technical objects continually swapped positions, dissolving the boundaries between tool, collaborator, and outcome. The lab was not *in* a room—it *was* the room: a living network of human and nonhuman agencies.

Perhaps we can design labs not only to test new musical ideas but also to retrieve knowledge about who we become in collaboration. This might prove particularly helpful for performers and performance educators, to develop a practice-based understanding of collaborative intra-action.

The Multimodal Lab as a Generative Experimental System...

This first lab inaugurated my devised experimental system: *epistemic things*—roles, affordances, and material resistances—generated new questions, while *technical objects*—tools, reflection methods, and apparatus—stabilized the process just enough to make those questions visible. Rather than aiming for a finished piece, the lab produced conditions for artistic becoming, where identities and possibilities emerged through practice.

I propose that the multimodal artistic research lab operates through four intertwined principles:

1. **Non-linear structure**—No fixed goal or “piece”. Aims emerged and dissolved; the process itself became compositional.

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2. **Defamiliarization**—Traditional hierarchies of composer and performer were suspended; each learned the other’s tools.
 3. **Iterative instability**—Malfunctions became material, not mistakes.
 4. **Momentary crystallization**—The final showing was not closure but a snapshot of entanglement, extended by audience discussion as an additional epistemic layer.

Each mode—performance, reflection, documentation, conversation—constituted a distinct aesthetic output, forming a multimodal ecology of creation. Roles, affordances, and material agencies intersected in ways that continually generated new questions. This suggests that multimodal labs may be particularly effective for performers and artists seeking to understand how identities and artistic possibilities emerge through collaborative intra-action.

... and Pathways for Further Inquiry!

Referencing Rheinberger (2006) once more, the experiment and laboratory ultimately reveal more questions than answers. At this point in my project, some analytical as well as philosophical questions have crystallized from *OpenLab#1.1*:

- Are creative outcomes shaped by the affordances we humans have of each other?
- Might we become new practitioners within each collaborative encounter? If so, how do we exist between encounters—or, as Barad might argue, are we always in and of our encounters?
- What happens if we abandon fixed ideas of who we are in projects and instead allow the experimental system to generate who we become?

Conclusion

The findings of this lab support an understanding of human-nonhuman collaboration as a form of generative entanglement. Drawing on Rheinberger, de Assis, and Barad, this paper argues that knowledge in artistic research emerges not only from outcomes but through the dynamic interplay of roles, materials, and temporalities. The multimodal lab is not simply a site for making music; it is a machine for producing alternative modes of creation and reflection.

Each iteration becomes another movement in a larger composition of practice—collective, material, and reflective. By embracing intra-action, we shift from viewing collaboration as the meeting of separate entities to understanding it as a process of mutual becoming. This reframing invites us to design artistic research environments that privilege openness, instability, and transformation—conditions under which new identities, practices, and questions can continually emerge.

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